

The Impact of Green Marketing Strategies on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium-Sized Restaurants in Saudi Arabia

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Abstract:

The aim of this study is twofold. First, to explore the extent to which family style local restaurants adopt green marketing strategies; lean green, defensive green, shaded green, and extreme green. Second, to examine the effects of these strategies on marketing performance. The study is driven by a cross-sectional survey-based design. A literature-driven questionnaire was designed, explored, confirmed and hence validated prior to data gathering. It consisted of two sections; the first one collects data on green marketing strategies while the second one gathers data on marketing performance. The population of the study consists of all managers of Small and Medium-Sized restaurants in Jeddah. A random sample was selected from the study population consists of knowledgeable informants, e.g., managers. A total of 300 managers were identified, so 300 questionnaires were handed. Two-hundred and thirteen questionnaires were returned with response rate of 71%. The results revealed that family style restaurants use green marketing strategies in varied degrees. The most adopted strategy is lean green marketing strategy with a high degree, followed by shaded green, defensive green with a moderate degree and finally extreme green with a low degree. Finally, the results indicated that lean green marketing strategy was the most influential strategy on marketing performance, followed by shaded GMS. The other two green marketing strategies had no significant effect on marketing performance.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Green marketing (GM) has been defined as a process directed to meet customers' as well as society requirements in a manner that not only achieves profitability but also maintains sustainability. It is a holistic process that includes all marketing practices like pricing, packaging, distribution, new products development in addition to promotion and advertising (Dief and Font, 2010). In a study on strategic marketing and marketing strategy, Varadarajan (2010) indicated that organizational decisions related to choices of marketing activities and resources are embedded in an organization's marketing strategy. When an organization is encouraged to be an environmentally responsible entity, the most crucial term furnished in the context of marketing strategy is green marketing strategy (GMS).

Ginsberg and Bloom (2004) identified four green marketing strategies, which were lean green, defensive

green, shaded green, and extreme green. The authors indicated that these strategies can be understood in terms of their emphasis on marketing mix elements; the emphasis of lean green strategy is on the product, while the focus of defensive green is on both product and promotion, in comparison with shaded green that focuses on product, price and promotion. Finally, extreme green strategy pays extended attention to product, price, place and promotion. Cronin et al. (2010) determined three marketing strategies, which were green innovation, organization greening and green alliances. Green innovation is related to innovative products and services that meet customers' requirements and protect the environment. Organization greening can be described as management commitment to environmental responsibility, green processes and green supply chain management. Green alliances are partnerships formed with other organization to create an environment friendly system.

Reasons that stimulate organizations to use green marketing are various. Polonsky (2008) argued that an organization uses green marketing as an opportunity to enhance the ability to achieve its goals, as a response to government regulations and competitors, or to reduce costs through waste removal and raw material usage. Despite the importance of the effects of GMS adoption on organizations such as a good position in the market place, it is necessary to pay close attention to the idea that customers are not interested in eco-friendly products due to environment protection if the products are not suitable for them. However, if the product meets the wants and needs of customers, and at the same time does not harm the environment, they prefer to use it instead of another product. It was understood that the first priority of interest to the customer is the product or service itself (Ginsberg and Bloom, 2004).

In order to explore the extent to which green marketing strategies as conceptualized by Ginsberg and Bloom (2004) in terms of four key strategies: lean green, defensive green, shaded green, and extreme green, the current study was carried out using data from family style local restaurants. In terms of the effect of green marketing strategies on organizational performance, the results were mixed. Hasan and Ali (2015) and Eneizan et al. (2016) found a positive effect of green marketing strategies on firm's performance. On the other hand, Kinoti, M. W. (2017) showed that these strategies have no significant effect on performance related dimensions such as market share or gross profit. On account of that, this study aims at investigating the effect of green marketing strategies adopted by family restaurants on marketing performance. Carrying out this study should boost practitioners' and researchers' awareness about green marketing strategies that elevate restaurants performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1 GMS adopted by restaurants

Lean green marketing strategy has been described by Chen and Chang (2012) as the most hidden greening strategy used by organizations, since the company is not interested in publishing the green initiative it is implementing. For the authors, the reason for this is that the organization does not want to appear as an environmentally conservative organization, which

increases the expectations of the public, but in turn the organization benefits by reducing costs. Ginsberg and Bloom (2004) marked lean green strategy as a product-intended strategy. According to Zwerg-Villegas (2008), organizations that use lean green strategy are affected by cost reduction intention and have no aims to maintain sustainability of market segment or differentiate based on greening. Since organizations involved in this strategy do not prefer making their practices of lean green public, it is difficult to recognize these organizations.

According to Chan (2013a), one strategy of green marketing that is used by organizations is the defensive strategy, which refers to a strategy adopted by organizations in which these organizations are adhere to the minimum requirements of green marketing in order to avoid penalties or fines resulting from failure to comply with the government regulations issued for the conservation of the environment. Ginsberg and Bloom (2004) indicated that defensive strategy is concerned with efforts made by organizations in relation to two elements of marketing mix, which are product and promotion. Chan (2013b) added that this strategy represents a precautionary way followed by organizations just to respond to another party pressure such as environmental bodies or competitive organizations. Zwerg-Villegas (2008) regarded the defensive green marketing strategy as a situational tactic followed by organizations to cope with external pressures linked with environment protection trends.

Organizations that adopt the shaded green marketing strategy often focus primarily on the product's characteristics and then the associated environmental benefits. In spite of the organization's ability to differentiate its products in terms of environmental benefits, it prefers to focus on the attributes of the product (Ginsberg and Bloom, 2004). Hence, a key feature of organizations that use the shaded green marketing strategy is that these organizations have a high opinion of greening as a strategic orientation (Zwerg-Villegas, 2008). For them, organizations that use extreme green marketing strategy are those involved in greening on a daily basis. This strategy represents an incorporation of greenness into business strategy. Hitherto, little is known about how really organizations are involved in adopting green marketing strategies.

In order to identify the extent to which family style local restaurants are using green marketing strategies, the

following hypotheses were suggested:

H1: Family style local restaurants adopt lean green marketing strategy.

H2: Family style local restaurants adopt defensive green marketing strategy.

H3: Family style local restaurants adopt shaded green marketing strategy.

H4: Family style local restaurants adopt extreme green marketing strategy.

2.2 The effect of GMS on marketing performance

Fraj et al. (2011) investigated the effect of GMS on organizational performance as measured by operational, marketing and economic performance using data from several industries in a European country, and found a significant and positive effect of green marketing strategy on marketing performance. Confirming this, Olson (2008) stated that the adoption of green strategy in an organization will affect the organizational strategy and its impact including performance management, employment practices, training, and awareness campaigns conducted by the organization to achieve its green goals. Similarly, Cronin et al. (2010) underlined the importance of green strategies in raising organizational performance.

Generally, the effect of GMS on organizational performance has been established in numerous studies (Hasan and Ali, 2015; Eneizan et al., 2016). Yet, is there a significant link between using GMS such as lean green, defensive green, shaded green and extreme green strategy and organizational performance, to say, as represented by marketing performance of restaurants? Answering this question can be completed based on Ginsberg and Bloom (2004) categorization of GMS in accordance with the elements of marketing mix. They stated that lean green, defensive green, shaded green and extreme green strategies are focused on green products. In addition to that, the defensive green strategy includes promotion; the shaded green strategy emphasizes price and promotion, while the extreme green strategy incorporates price, place as well as promotion.

Consequently, the current study conceptualizes lean green strategy as a strategy of green product; defensive green as a strategy of green product and green promotion; shaded green as a strategy of green product; green price as well as green promotion; and extreme green as a strategy of green product, green price, green distribution

along with green promotion. Following green product philosophy results in improved financial and non-financial performance of organizations (Eneizan et al., 2016). In a study by Hasan and Ali (2015) on GMS, green innovation and green promotions were positively associated to organizational performance, economic and operational performance. In fact, little has been said on the effect of lean green, defensive, green, shaded green, and extreme green strategies on marketing performance, particularly in restaurants. In order to investigate the effect of GMS on marketing performance, the following hypotheses were proposed:

H5: There is a significant effect of lean green marketing on marketing performance.

H6: There is a significant effect of defensive green marketing on marketing performance.

H7: There is a significant effect of shaded green marketing on marketing performance.

H8: There is a significant effect of extreme green marketing on marketing performance.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Population and sample of the study

The population of the study consists of all managers of Small and Medium-Sized restaurants in Jeddah (a city in the Hejaz region of Saudi Arabia) counted four thousands eight hundreds and two managers (Small and Medium-Sized Establishments Survey 2018). A random sample was selected from the study population consists of knowledgeable informants, e.g., managers. A total of 300 managers were identified, so 300 questionnaires were handed. Two-hundred and thirteen questionnaires were returned with response rate of 71%.

3.2 Measures, validity and reliability

Table 1 summarizes items used to measure each variable in addition to results of factor loadings, validity and reliability of the scale. The main focus of lean green marketing strategy is on the product only (Ginsberg and Bloom, 2004). Therefore, it was measured using items related to green products by four items adapted from previous studies such as the introduction of environment friendly products (Dief and Font, 2010), cost reduction based on environmental programs (Shabani et al., 2013), reduction of negative effect of materials used in the product and product recyclability (Baines et al., 2012). Defensive green marketing strategy was measured

by three items: “Using environmental considerations in product design” and “Employment of green arguments in advertising and promotions” adopted from Fraj et al. (2011, P. 346) as well as “inability to differentiate products based on the environmentally friendly characteristics” (Shabani et al., 2013, P. 1882).

Shaded green marketing strategy was measured on the basis of participation in long-term environmental efforts (Shabani et al., 2013), lack of focus on green distribution, production of innovative products, and concentration on the product attributes first then the environmental benefits provided (Ginsberg and Bloom, 2004). Extreme green marketing strategy (Ginsberg and Bloom, 2004) was measured by four items: “Using environmental considerations in distribution system” (Fraj et al., 2011, P. 346), “Combining environment, profitability and product life cycle” (Shabani et al., 2013, P. 1883) as well as customer willingness to pay in addition to the price of eco-oriented products (Chan, 2013b). Marketing performance was measured by items related to successful introduction of new products, (Mohammad, 2020; Mohammad et al., 2014; Al-Hawary et al., 2013; Fraj et al., 2011) such as materials used in the product, first to market, product differentiation, sales volume (Al-Hawary & Aldaihani, 2016; Al-Hawary & Al-Hamwan, 2017; Al-Hawary & Hadad, 2016; Al-Hawary & Ismael, 2010; Hilal et al., 2012).

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was used during questionnaire development to explore the data set. Factors were extracted based on Scree test that has been suggested as an accurate test of factor retention (Costello and Osborne, 2005). It is an alternative test of The eigen values-greater-than-one rule (O’Connor, 2000).The Scree plot of eigen values exhibited in Figure 1 shows that the number of factors that can be retained are five. The total variance explained by these factors was 94.8%. The factor analysis was conducted by IBM SPSS using Varimax rotation method, on the basis of principal components extraction method while suppressing small coefficients below an absolute value of 0.5

Figure 1. Scree plot of eigenvalues

Factor loadings, as shown in Table 1, all items were ranged from 0.711 to 0.911. The average variance extracted (AVE) represents the percent of variance that a construct explains and should be higher than 0.50 (Chen, 2008). AVE values for all constructs in this study were adequate. Following Fornell and Larcker (1981), convergent validity was tested based on the average variance extracted. The results confirmed that the current scale shows a high level of validity since AVE values of all dimensions were greater than 0.5. Reliability was measured by composite reliability (CR). As noted, values of CR were acceptable ranging from 0.88 for lean green marketing strategy to 0.91 for marketing performance (Johnson and Grayson, 2005). All in all, the current scale can be used to collect data from respondents due to adequate levels of validity and reliability.

Table 1. Measures and results of validity and reliability

Variables	Items	Loadings	AVE	CR
Lean green marketing strategy	GMS01	0.884	0.65	0.88
	GMS02	0.809		
	GMS03	0.741		
	GMS04	0.783		
Defensive green marketing strategy	GMS05	0.911	0.66	0.88
	GMS06	0.837		
	GMS07	0.774		
	GMS08	0.711		
Shaded green marketing strategy	GMS09	0.848	0.68	0.90
	GMS10	0.837		
	GMS11	0.860		
	GMS12	0.755		
Extreme green marketing strategy	GMS13	0.852	0.69	0.90
	GMS14	0.841		
	GMS15	0.820		
	GMS16	0.816		

Marketing performance	MRKT1	0.896	0.71	0.91
	MRKT2	0.851		
	MRKT3	0.833		
	MRKT4	0.799		

Despite the importance of exploratory factor analysis in estimating the factor structure by rotation, the results of this analysis should be confirmed through the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), which specifies the structure well and evaluates the goodness-of-fit of the model (Hox and Bechger, 1998). Therefore, CFA was conducted for the current data with the purpose of identifying the model fit. Predictive (Chi-square), and comparative (Comparative fir index) as well as the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), as can be seen in Table 2. The results in Table 2 indicate that proposed model fit the data well ($\chi^2/df \leq 2$, CFI > 0.922, RMSEA < 0.08).

Table 2. Results of fit indices

Fit Indices	Value	Result
Chi-square to degree of freedom ratio (χ^2/df)	2.47	adequate
The comparative fit index (CFI)	0.922	adequate
The root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	0.048	adequate

IV. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The hypotheses that family style local restaurants adopt lean green, defensive green, shaded green and extreme green marketing strategies were explored using means, standard deviations (SD) as well as One-sample t-test. The results in Table 2 clarifies that family style restaurants adopt primarily lean green strategy (M = 3.77, SD = 0.54, t = 20.72, P = 0.000), followed by shaded strategy (M = 3.42, SD = 0.87, t = 6.95, P = 0.000), then defensive green (M = 3.37, SD = 0.90, t = 6.31, P = 0.000) and finally extreme green (M = 2.30, SD = 0.89, t = -11.388, P = 0.000). Based on these results, hypotheses H1, H2, H3 and H4 were supported.

Table 2. Results of One-Sample T-test

Strategies	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	t-value	df	P-value
Lean green	3.77	0.54	0.037	20.72	212	0.000
Shaded	3.42	0.87	0.060	6.947	212	0.000

green						
Defensive green	3.37	0.90	0.062	6.308	212	0.000
Extreme green	2.30	0.89	0.061	-	212	0.000
green				11.388		

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for all strategies ranged from 1.14 to 2.59, which is less than 5, with tolerance values ranged from 0.386 to 0.875, which is greater than 0.2.

On the other hand, hypotheses H5, H6, H7 and H8, which presumed significant effects of lean green, defensive green, shaded green and extreme green on marketing performance, were tested through path analysis conduct by AMOS. Figure 2 displays a recursive model consisting of 5 observed variables (LG, DG, SG, and EG) and an unobserved variable (MP).

Figure 2. Path analysis of green marketing strategies and marketing performance

In terms of covariance, the most varied variables were lean green and extreme green (Cov. = 0.083, C.R. = 3.074, P = 0.002). By reference to Table 3, green marketing strategies explain about 47% of the variance in marketing performance. Lean green has a significant effect on marketing performance ($\beta = 0.414$, C.R. = 5.416, P = 0.000). Not only that, shaded green has a significant effect on marketing performance ($\beta = 0.171$, C.R. = 3.029, P = 0.002). On the contrary, defensive green has no significant effect on marketing performance ($\beta = 0.061$, C.R. = 1.448, P = 0.147) and extreme green has no significant effect on marketing performance ($\beta = 0.032$, C.R. = 0.915, P = 0.360).

Table 3. Maximum Likelihood Estimates

Path	Estimate	S.E	C.R.	P
LG→MP	0.414	0.076	5.416	***
DG→MP	0.061	0.042	1.448	0.147
SG→MP	0.171	0.056	3.029	0.002

EG → MP	0.032	0.035	0L915	0.360
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V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In a one vein of green marketing, the emphasis was on four green marketing strategies related to marketing mix elements; product, price, place and promotion. These strategies are lean green, defensive green, shaded green and extreme green. According to Ginsberg and Bloom (2004) who categorized these green strategies, one strategy, which is lean green, is concerned with the product, while green defensive is about two elements of the marketing mix, which are product and promotion. Shaded green, on the other hand, is attributed to three elements; product, price and promotion. Finally, extreme green covers all the 4Ps of marketing; product, price, place and promotion.

Using a sample of respondents, i.e., managers, from family style restaurants, it was found that these restaurants highly adopt lean green strategy in the first place, followed by shaded green and defensive green strategies in moderate degrees. Interestingly, the results revealed that family style restaurants have a low level of extreme green strategy adoption. The results illustrate that family restaurants pay a great attention to their products, i.e., food meals and therefore to the ingredients that used in these products. Notably, this is a logical result since the components of food meals are reflected in the quality of the product itself. Ryu and Han (2010) recognized that food quality is the most important factor for customers to be satisfied. Since shaded green restaurants, product, price and promotion are considered, one can conclude that shaded green strategy represents an extension of lean green strategy. Promotion activities are used in restaurants in line with their environments like communities derived by health (Glanz and Hoelscher, 2004).

Previously, price was found to play a significant role as moderator in the relationship between quality and customer satisfaction Ryu and Han (2010). In the sample of this study, there were some restaurants that adopt the defensive strategy. These restaurants provided the least requirements in response to external parties such as governmental and environmental bodies or competitive organizations Chan (2013b). Finally, the results indicated a low level of extreme green adoption between family restaurants. Perhaps, this is due to the small number of

family restaurants that are fully oriented toward green marketing strategies.

In the current study, green marketing strategies were assumed to have significant effects on marketing performance as indicated in the literature (Hasan and Ali, 2015 and Eneizan et al., 2016). The results revealed that lean green strategy was the important one in terms of its significant effect on marketing performance, followed by shaded green strategy. Defensive green strategy and extreme green strategy have no significant effect on marketing performance. Generally, the significant effect of green marketing strategy on organizational performance was originated in several studies (Fraj et al., 2011; Olson, 2008; Cronin et al., 2010; Eneizan et al., 2016). No previous studies found to confirm or reject these results. However, in accordance with Ginsberg and Bloom (2004), all family style restaurants are concerned with their products, prices as well as promotions. When it comes to defensive strategy with least essentials, customers are aware to recognize that defensive restaurants do not do their best to satisfy them. The low level of extreme green adoption resulted in a non-significant effect of this strategy on marketing performance. It was concluded that lean and shaded green strategies are strategies that restaurants can use to improve their marketing performance.

VI. LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

One key limitation of this study is that it was conducted using managers' perceptions. Particularly, marketing performance was assessed on the basis of their perceptions. Future studies should consider customers' perceptions instead. In a study on restaurants in the Polish market, Gheribi (2017) found a positive link between innovation-oriented organizational culture and restaurant performance. Therefore, it was recommended that future study may use organizational culture as a mediator variable in the relationship between green marketing strategies and marketing performance.

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